

Wave-Like Dark Matter as an Alternative Framework for Quantum Physics

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Abstract

We explore wave-like dark matter (WDM) as an alternative paradigm for quantum mechanics, proposing that quantum phenomena, such as wave-particle duality and entanglement, emerge from interactions with the oscillatory field of WDM. This approach reframes quantum mechanics within a deterministic framework where the scalar field Φ mediates probabilities and nonlocal interactions. We develop a mathematical model linking WDM's scalar field dynamics to key quantum phenomena and analyze its implications for unifying quantum physics with gravity.

1. Introduction

The quantum world is dominated by wave-particle duality, probabilistic behavior, and nonlocal correlations. While these principles are foundational to quantum mechanics, they remain conceptually at odds with the deterministic, geometric nature of general relativity.

Wave-like dark matter offers a potential unifying framework by interpreting quantum phenomena as emergent properties of a pervasive scalar field. This field, governed by the Klein-Gordon equation, introduces deterministic oscillations that underlie quantum behavior.

In this paper, we present a mathematical formalism for quantum mechanics as an emergent property of WDM, examine its compatibility with key experiments (e.g., the double-slit experiment), and outline implications for unification with gravity.

2. Theoretical Framework

2.1. Wave-Like Dark Matter and Quantum Probabilities

The WDM scalar field $\Phi(\vec{r}, t)$ is postulated to mediate quantum behavior through local oscillations and nonlocal correlations. The scalar field satisfies the generalized Klein-Gordon equation:

$$\square\Phi + \frac{\partial V(\Phi)}{\partial\Phi} = 0.$$

We propose that the squared amplitude of Φ , normalized in a given region, corresponds to the probability density $\rho(\vec{r}, t)$:

$$\rho(\vec{r}, t) = |\Phi(\vec{r}, t)|^2.$$

This interpretation aligns with the Born rule in quantum mechanics, where the wavefunction's magnitude determines probabilities.

2.2. Wave-Particle Duality

Wave-particle duality arises naturally in this framework, as particles are localized excitations in the scalar field Φ . The de Broglie relation, which links a particle's wavelength to its momentum, emerges from the field's oscillatory nature:

$$\lambda = \frac{h}{p},$$

where λ is the wavelength, h is Planck's constant, and p is the particle's momentum.

The scalar field Φ generates an effective potential V_{eff} :

$$V_{\text{eff}} = V(\Phi) + \frac{1}{2}\rho_m v^2,$$

which governs both wave-like and particle-like behaviors.

2.3. Nonlocality and Entanglement

WDM provides a medium for instantaneous correlations over large distances. Two interacting particles create coupled perturbations in Φ , forming a shared state:

$$\Phi_{\text{entangled}} = \Phi_1(\vec{r}_1, t)\Phi_2(\vec{r}_2, t),$$

where Φ_1 and Φ_2 represent localized field solutions at different spatial regions.

Measurement collapses $\Phi_{\text{entangled}}$ to one of its eigenstates, consistent with the predictions of quantum mechanics. The underlying determinism of Φ ensures conservation laws are preserved during collapse.

3. Mathematical Derivations

3.1. Correspondence with Schrödinger Equation

The dynamics of Φ in low-energy systems can be approximated by the Schrödinger equation. Begin with the Klein-Gordon equation for the scalar field:

$$\square\Phi + \frac{\partial V(\Phi)}{\partial\Phi} = 0.$$

In a non-relativistic limit ($v \ll c$), decompose Φ into a rapidly oscillating phase term and a slowly varying amplitude:

$$\Phi(\vec{r}, t) = A(\vec{r}, t)e^{iS(\vec{r}, t)/\hbar}.$$

Substituting into the Klein-Gordon equation and applying the eikonal approximation yields:

$$i\hbar\frac{\partial A}{\partial t} = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\nabla^2 A + V_{\text{eff}}A.$$

This is the Schrödinger equation, demonstrating that quantum mechanics is an emergent, low-energy approximation of the WDM dynamics.

3.2. Double-Slit Experiment

The double-slit experiment can be modeled by propagating WDM field disturbances through two apertures. The resulting interference pattern is given by:

$$I(\vec{r}) = |\Phi_1(\vec{r}) + \Phi_2(\vec{r})|^2,$$

where Φ_1 and Φ_2 are the scalar field solutions for each slit. Expanding this expression yields:

$$I(\vec{r}) = |\Phi_1(\vec{r})|^2 + |\Phi_2(\vec{r})|^2 + 2\text{Re}[\Phi_1^*(\vec{r})\Phi_2(\vec{r})].$$

The interference term demonstrates the coherence of WDM's oscillatory nature, reproducing the experimental pattern without invoking additional quantum postulates.

3.3. Quantum Tunneling

Quantum tunneling occurs when a WDM field perturbation propagates through a potential barrier. The tunneling probability P is proportional to the decay of Φ within the barrier region:

$$P \sim \exp\left(-\int \sqrt{2m(V_{\text{eff}} - E)} dx/\hbar\right).$$

This matches the quantum mechanical tunneling formula, indicating that the field dynamics govern particle behavior in classically forbidden regions.

4. Observational Consistency

4.1. Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle

The uncertainty relation arises naturally from WDM's oscillatory nature. The Fourier transform of $\Phi(\vec{r}, t)$ relates position and momentum distributions:

$$\Delta x \Delta p \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}.$$

4.2. Bell's Inequality

Nonlocal correlations in Φ reproduce violations of Bell's inequality. Coupled scalar field solutions for entangled particles create instantaneous correlations consistent with experimental results.

5. Implications for Unification

The WDM framework inherently bridges quantum mechanics and gravity by linking quantum probabilities to scalar field oscillations. Since WDM governs gravitational phenomena (Paper 1), its extension to quantum mechanics suggests a unified description of all forces.

6. Conclusion

This paper demonstrates that wave-like dark matter provides a viable alternative to quantum mechanics, explaining wave-particle duality, nonlocality, and tunneling as emergent properties of a scalar field. By connecting quantum and gravitational phenomena, this framework advances efforts toward a unified theory of everything.

Keywords: Wave-like dark matter, quantum mechanics, entanglement, double-slit experiment, unified physics